

The titration curves are greatly altered in presence of Eu^{III} and correspond to complex formation according to

The stability constants were calculated (Table 1) using Irving-Rossotti expression⁷.

Ligand no.	$\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$	$\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
(I)	8.1	11.9	16.58	18.85
(II)	8.7	12.1	16.32	18.44
(III)	7.8	11.0	15.68	18.34

for the determination of trace concentrations of Eu^{III} by azopyrazolone ligands and vice versa.

The above amperometric results could be used to determine precisely the composition of the Eu^{III} -azopyrazolone complex by means of reverse molar ratio⁸. The value of i_a decreases on successive additions of Eu^{III} and the values of $(i_{a0} - i_a)$ can be taken as a measure for the magnitude of complex formation. The plot of $(i_{a0} - i_a)$ vs $[\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}]$ shows intersection at a molar ratio of 1 : 2 (metal-ligand). It can, therefore, be concluded that the 2-hydroxyazopyrazolone dyes form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Eu^{III} by the replacement of the phenolic and the hydrazo protons.

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4(2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenylazo)-5-pyrazolone ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) and with Eu^{III} ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) at $\text{pH}=10$, in 40% dioxane-water mixture.

The values of $\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$, $\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ depend on the structure of the ligand where the values of the chloro derivative(III) are the lowest due to their lower $\text{p}K$ values and those of the ligand(I) are higher due to its higher basicity.

Polarographic studies : The studies were carried out in solutions containing $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand in universal buffer of $\text{pH}=10$, in dioxane-water mixture (40%, v/v). This pH was selected to ensure the presence of the dinion species of the ligands. The polarogram of free ligand(III), as an example, is shown in Fig. 1. Gradual addition of 0.2 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Eu^{III} aqueous solution, was continued till the metal-ligand ratio reaches about 1 : 1. The polarogram of the azo ligand suffers a decrease in height by the increase of the metal ion concentration. A plot of i_a vs $[\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}]$ shows an intersection at a molar ratio 2 : 1 (ligand-metal). This amperometric titration could thus be applied successfully

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